

THE THEORY OF NON-STANDARD FORMS AND TEACHING METHODS
IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSONS TODAY

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Abstract: This article deals with the language teaching, which is becoming one of the most important problems of our time, that is, effective teaching of the Russian language and more in-depth training of non-standard forms of students.

Keywords: modern, students, education, Russian language, efficiency, originality, integration, visual-figurative

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Nowadays the profession of teacher is at the center of modern education. The Russian alphabet occupies a central place in the primary education system. As a means of knowing the truth, the Russian language provides not only linguistic knowledge, but also the intellectual development of the child, forms a conceptual and categorical apparatus, develops abstract thinking, memory and imagination. In recent years, unfortunately, there has been a sharp decline in students' interest in Russian language classes, there is no desire to expand the language skills of children, improve literacy and speech culture. At present, the most important problem that interests all teachers is to increase the effectiveness of the Russian language lesson as the main form of teaching and educating students. Lessons conducted in the same, old form might bore the students in the classroom. The monotony of lessons for the student and teacher reduces the effectiveness of educational activities. Not to force to teach, but to arouse interest, is the duty of the teacher to create a desire in students constant learning. The younger student has specific age-related features: unstable attention, the predominance of visual-figurative thinking, increased motor activity, the desire for play activities, a variety of knowledge. All this complicates the work of the teacher.

The ways of understanding new material are mutually beneficial in mastering the science of cooperation, asking your teacher and friends about things that he did not know and did not understand methods aimed at teaching and teaching others. These methods are not only considered to be effective, both intellectual and educational value, that is, these methods form students' feelings of friendship, honesty, kindness. Methods that allow students to reflect on what they have learned are new methods that measure how well they have mastered the subject.

Using them, students can think critically, assimilate knowledge, skills such as the ability to compare will be developed.

To keep the attention of children in the lesson, it is necessary to organize an active and interesting mental activity. Since traditional teaching methods cannot always ensure the assimilation of the material by all students, it is necessary to skillfully organize learning activities in the classroom. In order to create conditions for the formation of this activity, it is necessary to form cognitive motivation. The creativity of teachers in preparing and delivering lessons can have a positive impact on students and learners. In order to activate students, develop interest, encourage them to acquire knowledge, the teacher should put effort into the labour and other forms of lessons - their interesting varieties, and as a result create author-non-traditional lessons. The teacher of the Russian language cannot be guided only by the official requirements for the lesson. To improve his methodological activity, the teacher must know the traditional and non-traditional forms of Russian language lessons, their typology, and the specifics of lessons in the education system. The form of organization of training in order to assimilate the material being studied (knowledge, skills, worldview and moral and aesthetic ideas). According to the main didactic purpose, such lessons are divided into: - a lesson on familiarization with new materials; - a lesson to consolidate what has been learned; - a lesson in the application of knowledge and skills; - the lesson of generalization and systematization of knowledge; - a lesson in checking and correcting knowledge and skills; - combined (mixed) occupation. According to the main method of conducting classes: a conversation, a lecture, independent work of students, laboratory and practical work, combining different forms of classes. The main stages of the educational process are divided as follows: - introductory classes; - preliminary familiarization with materials; - concepts, laws, rules for studying lessons; - lessons of practical application of knowledge; - mixed or combined classes. Control classes serve to form the educational process and its results, the level of assimilation of the knowledge system (in the subject, department, the entire course), the skills of students' educational activities. Control can be carried out orally and in written form. Any lesson, traditional or complex, interesting or boring, has its own structure. The stages of the lesson include the concepts of goals and didactic tasks aimed at the implementation of the educational and developmental functions of the lesson.

There are different approaches to the choice of the main structural elements of the lesson. At the same time, the general didactic structure of the lesson is distinguished by three main (generalized) structural elements: - actualization of previously acquired knowledge and methods of action; - formation of new knowledge and methods of action; - application of knowledge and formation of

skills and abilities. As you know, traditional school lessons include learning new materials, consolidating knowledge, skills and abilities, testing and reviewing the knowledge gained, reviewing tests, summarizing and systematizing what has been learned, repeating a topic or section. Recently, along with these forms of education, non-traditional or non-standard ones are also widely used.

Learning encouragement methods can be used in the teaching of almost all subjects taught in the general secondary education system. To do this, the teacher himself must have an idea about the application of the above methods. Methods such as free writing, cluster, brainstorming, drawing B-B-B, a sequence of intricate logical chains, a quick survey quickly attract students and increase their activity in the lesson. In Russian language lessons, these techniques should be used first in a simple form, and then in a more complex one, in accordance with the age of the students. Lessons organized according to these methods are effective both in primary and secondary grades. New material understanding methods are methods aimed at the mutual cooperation of students in mastering science, learning by asking teachers and friends about what they do not know and do not understand, and teaching others. These methods are considered effective not only intellectually, but also educationally, that is, these methods evoke feelings of friendship, honesty, and kindness in students. Techniques that allow students to think about what they have learned are methods that determine the extent to which students have mastered a new topic. With their help, you can increase students' interest in independent learning, develop their creative independence, teach them to work with various sources of knowledge.

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